

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Annual Performance Assessment of a Vertical Constructed Wetland for University Campus Wastewater Treatment

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Abstract

Objectives: The main objective of this study was to evaluate the performance of constructed wetlands using various substrates. **Method:** Over a period of 12 months (Jan 2024 to Dec 2024), raw and treated wastewater samples were collected at an interval of 10 days and their quality was assessed based on the following parameters: pH, electrical conductivity (EC), biological oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total suspended solids (TSS), total kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), and total phosphorus (TP). **Findings:** After treatment, the concentrations of these parameters were reduced by 30 to 70 percent. Comparing all three substrates, the trend for BOD and COD removal is as follows: red burnt brick aggregate, then fly ash brick aggregate, and least in stone aggregate. Red burnt brick aggregate achieves the greatest removal rates. In contrast, the trend for TSS removal followed as stone aggregate > fly ash brick aggregate > red burnt brick aggregate. **Novelty:** The study provides a cost-effective way to use treated water for landscape irrigation. It was expected that the study's outcome would reveal the long-term performance of constructed wetlands under outdoor weather conditions, influenced by season, in treating wastewater in rural areas using vertical-flow constructed wetlands.

Keywords: Fly ash brick; Red burnt brick; Sustainable; Vertical constructed wetland

1 Introduction

India has seen tremendous increases in water use and deterioration of water quality during the last 20 years due to the country's fast urbanization, industrialization, and economic expansion⁽¹⁾. Due to its limitations, which include high prices and ineffective treatment, the current wastewater treatment technologies have not been able to satisfy the demands of social development⁽²⁾. CWs have become a very appealing and durable substitute. CWs are known for their energy efficiency, affordability, and innate capacity to self-correct and adjust to changing environmental conditions⁽³⁾. Consequently, CWs

were developed to handle different wastewaters in the twenty-first century and have grown in popularity^{(4), (5)}.

Wastewater treatment in natural conditions mainly includes stabilization ponds and constructed wetlands. These systems progressively remove pollutants through a single use⁽⁶⁾. Constructed wetlands are considered a modest, specialized, and ecologically manageable solution for wastewater treatment, as they effectively eliminate various contaminants⁽⁷⁾. Constructed wetlands (CWs) can be referred to as green and engineered systems for wastewater treatment, planned and designed to utilize nature-based purification processes, including certain macrophytes, substrates, and microbes⁽⁸⁾.

In CW, substrates are essential components that facilitate most physical, chemical, and biological interactions. Along with removing contamination, they also enable space for the attachment of biofilms and promote the growth of wetland plants⁽⁹⁾. Filtration, Sedimentation, Surface sorption, and precipitation by colloidal particles are some of the processes included in wastewater treatment. The voids between the substrate provide gas diffusion, microbial degradation, bio-immobilization, transformation and metabolic processes with the help of macrophyte plants⁽¹⁰⁾. Several substances, including natural elements such as sand and gravel, waste from agriculture and industries, and mineral-based substances like ceramic and activated carbon, can be utilized as CW substrates. Each material has individual characteristics that directly or indirectly contribute to the treatment. Naturally available materials can be used directly without any additional treatment⁽¹¹⁾.

Based on water flow, CW is of two types: subsurface flow (SSF) and surface flow (SF). The water level in a subsurface wetland is below the substrate and along the surface in the case of a surface flow type wetland. The water path in the SSF wetland can either be horizontal or vertical. The benefits of SSF over SF include greater climate endurance in colder climates, fewer odor concerns, and more efficient land use. Because the water level is below the ground surface, SSF wetlands can be built beneath public parks subsurface⁽¹²⁾.

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the wastewater quality performance of a vertical subsurface-constructed wetland in terms of delivering effective wastewater treatment under real-world conditions.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research site

At Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak, Haryana, three identical vertical flow-constructed wetlands were operated. Throughout the research period, temperatures ranged from 5.6°C to 48.8°C, and annual rainfall was 525.2 mm.

2.2 Experimental setup

The research was conducted from Jan 2024 to Dec 2024 at Maharshi Dayanand University (MDU) in Rohtak, Haryana. Wetland units with stone aggregate, fly ash brick aggregate, and common red burnt brick aggregate as substrate media are operated. All the wetland units were located near the sewage collection tank on the M.D.U. Campus provide geographical coordinates, allowing for the use of campus wastewater in the treatment process. University collection tank, which acts as an equalization tank collects wastewater from the university (academic buildings, hostels, library, faculty houses, non-teaching departments, etc.). Constructed wetland setup (Figure 1), has following components: (a) primary treatment tank (5900 lts) capacity with four baffled chambers. Receiving wastewater from the university's collection tank, function as a sedimentation tank, filled with 100-120 mm-sized construction waste material. (b) vertical subsurface flow constructed wetland (VSFCW) units with working capacity of approx. 2100 lts., which were made with the help of PVC drums (200L) capacity. Three similar wetland units were set up consisting of 6 cells (drums), interconnected in series with flexible water pipe (2 inch). These systems were established individually with 3 different substrate media: Red brick aggregates (CW1), Flyash brick aggregates (CW2), and Stone aggregates (CW3) with a slope of 2%. Each system was provided a hydraulic retention time of 10 hours. To examine the effectiveness of various substrate media, water samples were taken before and after treatment. All analytical procedures were performed according to the American Public Health Association's, 2017 Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater.

Various substrate media, illustrated in Figure 2 and Table 1, were used in the three different wetland units. The Uppermost layer consists of 20-40 mm stone aggregates, which are similar for all three units. The middle layer is composed of 40-50 mm aggregates, including red bricks in CW-1, fly ash bricks in CW-2, and stone in CW-3. Similarly, the base layer comprises three different media, varying in size from 50 to 80 mm. All the substrates were taken from local building material suppliers. Red brick and fly ash brick aggregates were then made with different size categories. The characteristics of different substrate media are shown in Table 1 below. The primary reason for adopting different-sized layering of substrate was to prevent and ensure the system operates smoothly for an extended period.

Fig 1. Design of the vertical subsurface flow constructed wetland: a) Schematic layout of Experimental setup; b) Media layer; c) flow regimen of constructed wetland unit

Fig 2. Different substrate media: from left to right, Flyash brick aggregates, Stone aggregates, Red brick aggregates

Table 1. Characteristics of different substrate media

Substrate media	Size mm	Void ratio
Stone aggregates	20-40	0.45
Red brick aggregates	40-50	0.5
Flyash brick aggregates	40-50	0.4
Stone aggregates	40-50	0.48
Red brick aggregates	50-80	0.56
Flyash brick aggregates	50-80	0.46
Stone aggregates	50-80	0.5

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Physico-chemical and statistical analysis of wastewater

For a year, the wetlands have been operated using different substrates. The parameters studied were pH, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total suspended solids (TSS), total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), and total phosphorus (TP), measured at 10-day intervals. Samples were collected from the inlet and outlet of the constructed wetland units and analyzed. Table 2 presents the mean values of physicochemical parameters for primary treatment, different substrates and their average removable efficiencies over a 12-month experimental period (January 2024–December 2024). The data from the pilot-scale study were used to calculate statistical parameters, i.e., average, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum values, as well as the respective removal percentage rates

pH: The mean pH of university wastewater was found to be 6.94, indicating that the wastewater is neutral (Table 2 and Figure 3). After treatment, the pH ranges between 6.59 and 7.58, which also falls within the neutral range. The pH can increase or decrease through wastewater treatment, depending on the nature of the contaminant and the conversion processes in the CW⁽¹³⁾.

Fig 3. Removal efficiency of various Physico-chemical parameters for wetland units

3.1.1. Electrical conductivity and Total Dissolved solids

The reductions in the EC among the three different substrates were 31.87% in CW-1, 22.71% in CW-2 and 20.72% in CW-3. The average concentrations of TDS in the wastewater ranged from 1004.67 mg/L to 2054 mg/L. After treatment, the removal rates were 28.20% in CW-1, 35.27% in CW-2, and 31.83% in CW-3 (Table 2 and Figure 3). In contrast, another study reported that the removal rates of EC and TDS vary from 11% to 36% and 10% to 26%, respectively, using different sizes of stone gravels. These findings highlight similar removal rates achieved in this study⁽¹¹⁾.

3.1.2. Total Suspended solids

The primary factors for effectively removing suspended solids in vertical constructed wetlands are hydraulic design and microbial characteristics⁽¹⁴⁾, ⁽¹⁵⁾. Due to their low velocity and large surface area, these systems have proven effective in removing suspended solids. Vertical subsurface wetlands offer gravity settling and adsorption on the substrate. In the present study, the average concentrations of TSS were found to be 163.92 mg/L in CW-1, 157.27 mg/L in CW-2, and 144.15 mg/L in CW-3, respectively, corresponding to 19.93%, 23.18%, and 29.59% removal, respectively (Table 2 and Figure 3). A study reported that TSS removal rates of 60- 80 % can be achieved using different sizes of stone gravels, highlighting a significant difference from the results obtained in this study⁽¹¹⁾.

Table 2. Variation in water quality parameters among Primary treatment and different wetland units consisting various substrate

Parameters (n=36)	Primary treatment			CW-1		Primary treat- ment+ CW1 Removal%	CW-2		Primary treat- ment+ CW2 Removal%	CW-3		Primary treat- ment+ CW3 Removal%
	Inlet	outlet	Avg. % removal	outlet	Avg. % removal		outlet	Avg. % removal		outlet	Avg. % removal	
BOD (mg/l)	128.28 ±19.20	90.27 ±18.22	29.63	34.14 ±16.44	62.18	91.81	36.91 ±12.95	59.11	88.74	40 ±14.88	55.69	85.32
COD (mg/l)	303.95 ±60.43	242.42 ±59.52	20.24	114.79 ±51.22	52.65	72.89	156.18 ±59.42	35.57	55.81	172.57 ±67.05	28.81	49.05
TKN (mg/l)	18.91 ±2.63	18.67 ±2.70	1.27	11.75 ±3.40	37.06	38.33	12.26 ±3.44	34.33	35.6	13.11 ±3.35	29.78	31.05
TP (mg/l)	3.92 ±0.75	3.83 ±0.78	2.36	1.71 ±0.55	55.35	57.71	1.26 ±0.55	67.10	69.46	2.74 ±0.81	28.46	30.82
PH	6.94 ±0.24	6.92 ±0.23	0.33	6.83 ±0.24	1.30	1.63	6.77 ±0.23	2.17	2.5	6.88 ±0.22	0.58	0.91
EC (ms/cm)	2.54 ±0.61	2.51 ±0.60	1.05	1.71 ±0.42	31.87	32.92	1.94 ±0.43	22.71	23.76	1.99 ±0.43	20.72	21.77
TDS (mg/l)	1505.76 ±268.57	1489.7 ±265.53	1.07	1069.65 ±344.81	28.20	29.27	964.35 ±319.11	35.27	36.34	1015.54 ±317.46	31.83	32.9
TSS (mg/l)	621.47 ±115.61	204.73 ±66.81	67.06	163.92 ±95.10	19.93	86.99	157.27 ±78.87	23.18	90.24	144.15 ±75.99	29.59	96.65

3.1.3. Biological oxygen demand

The quantity of oxygen consumed by microorganisms during the biological reaction of oxygen with organic material is referred to as BOD. In the present study, the BOD levels in the wastewater range from 98 mg/L to 165 mg/L. At the outlet, the average BOD levels for CW-1, CW-2, and CW-3 are 34.14 mg/L, 36.91 mg/L, and 40 mg/L, respectively. The average percentage reduction is 62.18%, 59.11% and 55.69%, respectively (Table 2 and Figure 3). BOD removal was observed to be higher in CW-1 than in CW-2 and CW-3. Red brick aggregates exhibit a higher level of BOD removal compared to fly ash brick aggregates and stone aggregates. A 50% BOD removal was achieved using stone gravel substrate media, which shows similar BOD removal efficiency to that observed in the present study⁽¹⁰⁾.

Chemical oxygen demand: Based on the studies, different substrates show distinct impacts in COD removal⁽¹⁶⁾,⁽¹⁷⁾. Substrates with larger surface areas enhance the growth and functioning of microorganisms, enabling them to effectively adsorb, absorb, and degrade water pollutants in sewage. COD of wastewater varies from 203 mg/l to 373 mg/l and COD was reduced by 52.65% in CW-1, 35.57% in CW-2 and 28.81 % in CW-3. A significant difference is evident in Table ??, where the maximum removal efficiency was achieved using red brick aggregates among the three-substrate media studied the use of waste bricks as wetland substrates in vertically constructed wetlands for wastewater treatment and found that the average COD removal rate was about 60 %, which aligns closely with the results of this study⁽¹⁸⁾.

Nitrogen: Previous studies have demonstrated a correlation between the type of wetland substrate and the effectiveness of constructed wetlands⁽¹⁹⁾. The wetland’s ability to remove pollutants improves with the presence of microbial biomass. The efficacy of nitrogen removal is significantly impacted by the nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria, as these processes are the main methods through which the wetland system eliminates nitrogen⁽²⁰⁾. The average nitrogen removal efficiencies in the present study were 37.06% in CW-1, 34.33% in CW-2, and 29.78% in CW-3, respectively (Table 2 and Figure 3). The red brick aggregates show the highest nitrogen removal efficiency among the three-substrate media studied. Total nitrogen removal was examined at 8.5% using gravel as the substrate media, whereas our study shows a total nitrogen removal of 29.78%⁽²¹⁾.

Phosphorus: Its removal primarily depends on three key factors: substrate media, wetland plants, and microorganisms. Generally, the removal rates are more effective through substrate absorption than through uptake by plant roots. The primary processes for phosphorus removal include precipitation, sedimentation, and adsorption onto porous media⁽²²⁾. A gravel base is the most commonly used filter material in subsurface flow-constructed wetlands. In this study, the average phosphorus concentration in wastewater was 3.92 mg/l. After being successfully treated, the concentrations decreased to 1.71, 1.26, and 2.74 mg/L in CW-1, CW-2, and CW-3, respectively (Table 2 and Figure 3), yielding removal efficiencies of 55.35%, 67.10%, and 28.46%. Among the substrate media tested, the fly ash brick aggregates show the highest phosphorus removal efficiency. The

use of stone aggregates as substrate media and found a phosphorus reduction of 33%, which aligns with the findings of this study⁽²³⁾.

4 Conclusion

This study found that the vertically constructed wetland system functioned effectively for wastewater treatment. Water quality indicators demonstrated significant improvements, with a total average removal of 30-70%, resulting in enhanced water quality. The three different substrates were found to be effective. The removal of organic and nutrient matter, including BOD, COD, TKN, and TP, was found to be most efficient with red brick aggregates, followed by fly ash brick aggregates, and least effective with stone aggregates. While stone aggregates were preferred over fly ash brick aggregates for removing suspended solids, red brick aggregates showed the least effectiveness. Furthermore, the hydraulic dynamics of the system can be adjusted to meet specific utility needs. These cost-efficient and readily available substrate media can be used as filter media in constructed wetland technology to address the prevailing wastewater management concern in developing countries, specifically the discharge of untreated domestic wastewater. The treated sewage wastewater could be used in agriculture.

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